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An ALNS-based heuristic for the Crop Planting Schedule Problem

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In this analytics challenge, we have been faced with the problem of crop planting schedule optimization. By analysing the problem structure and comparing it with other similar optimization problems, we have concluded that the given problem is very likely to be an NP-hard problem. Therefore, given the size of the problem instances to be solved, we have developed a heuristic algorithm based on the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search metaheuristic. In order to determine the harvest date, we also needed to predict the time of accumulating the enough amount growing degree units. For this purpose, we utilized an ARIMA model. The models, solution algorithm and obtained results are presented in the report.

Keywords: Crop planting schedule optimization, Metaheuristic approach, Adaptive large neighborhood search, ARIMA

1. Introduction

Commercial corn is an important element in the production of various food and industrial products, which sets a goal for the producers to harvest as much crop as possible. However, the produced crop needs to be stored appropriately until forwarded further in the process chain. Therefore, it is important not to overflow the available storage capacities and avoid waste of produced corn. This has led to the definition of the problem of optimizing corn crop planting schedule with the objective

to produce the required amount of corn, distributed over the time horizon as equally as possible, in order to avoid exceeding the available storing capacity.

The given *Crop Planting Schedule Problem* (CPSP) possesses similarities with the well-known job shop scheduling (van Laarhoven et al. 1992) and batch plant scheduling processing problems (Zhang and Gu 2020). The mentioned problems are known to be NP-hard (Gao et al. (2011), Zhang and Gu (2020)). Therefore, in the case of real instances, these problems are solved by heuristic approaches, such as simulated annealing (van Laarhoven et al. 1992), neighborhood searches (Gao et al. 2011), and genetic algorithms (Zhang and Gu 2020).

In Santini et al. (2020), we have found one linear programming solution approach for a very similar problem of crop growth planning in vertical farming. However, the instances solved in this paper are considerably smaller than ones given in this challenge.

Therefore, we have finally opted for developing a heuristic solution based on the *Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search* meta-heuristic (ALNS, Ropke and Pisinger (2006)). In our previous research endeavors, e.g. Obrenović et al. (2018), Buschor et al. (2019), and Markov et al. (2020), ALNS has proven to be a very powerful tool and smart strategy for searching large state spaces.

From the moment of planting, a seed population starts growing thanks to the accumulation of heat, which can be measured in growing degree units (GDUs). Then, when a predetermined amount of GDUs is reached, the population is harvested. The accumulation of GDUs depends on the planting site and varies throughout the year. Therefore, given a time window of possible planting dates for each population, it is first necessary to estimate the harvest date of each corn population for each feasible planting date. For this purpose, we estimate the dates of acquiring the sufficient amount of GDUs per population by creating an ARIMA model to forecast the daily GDUs based on historical data.

The remaining of the report is organized in the following manner. The GDUs forecasting model, CPSP definition, and solution algorithm are described respectively in Section 2. The selected solution is presented in Section 3. The conclusions of our research are given in Section 4. Finally, team members are presented in Section 5. All team members contributed equally to the presented research work and results.

Figure 1 GDUs accumulated for each calendar day from 01/01/2009 to 31/12/2019

2. Methodology and Theory

At the highest level, the selected methodological approach can be divided into two main components:

1. the forecasting of the GDUs for years 2020 and 2021 and,
2. the optimization of the planting schedule based on the forecasted GDUs.

The former is based on an ARIMA model and performed independently from the planting schedule optimization. Since different scenarios and sites can be regarded as separate problems, we applied the planting schedule optimization to each combination of site and scenario independently.

The GDUs forecasting is described in details in Subsection 2.1. The planting schedule optimization is presented through an optimization model (Subsection 2.2) and a heuristic algorithm (Subsection 2.3).

2.1. Growing Degree Units Forecasting

Figures 1a and 1b show the historical GDUs accumulated for site 0 and site 1, respectively. The data does not seem to have a trend over the years. On the other hand, the seasonality seems to be a component of both sites.

In order to validate our hypothesis we apply ETS (error, trend, and seasonality) decomposition to the time series data. Figures 2 and 3 show the decomposition for sites 0 and 1, respectively.

Figure 2 ETS decomposition of Site 0

Figure 3 ETS decomposition of Site 1

Figure 4 ACF and PACF plots of Site 0

We see from the figures that both data sets have seasonality component. As a result, the data is not stationary. Because of the seasonality, forecasting methods such as simple exponential smoothing or double exponential smoothing do not work (Gardner Jr 1985). Therefore, we focus on an autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) model (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos 2018).

To determine the parameters of the ARIMA model, we refer to Box-Jenkins method (Hyndman and Athanasopoulos 2018). First, we come up with the auto-correlation function (ACF) and partial auto-correlation function (PACF) of the time series. The outliers in PACF provide the parameter for the autoregressive (AR) part of the model and the outliers in ACF provide the parameter for the moving average (MA) part of the model. Here, we also take advantage of Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) in order to find the best parameters among several candidates.

Looking at the PACF graph of site 0 (Figure 4), we see that the AR parameter should be maximum 4. Since we are interested in the simplest model, we compare the AIC values of different ARIMA models. In other words, we compare ARIMA(4,1,4) and all the other simpler models, such

Figure 5 ACF and PACF plots of Site 1

as ARIMA(1,1,1) and ARIMA(1,1,2). We find that minimum AIC is achieved for ARIMA(2,1,2). Similarly, the PACF graph of site 1 (Figure 5) suggests 8 for the AR parameter and the minimum AIC suggests that ARIMA(7,1,8) should be used for forecasting.

With the help of determined ARIMA models, we forecast the accumulated GDU units per day for a time period of 80 weeks starting from 01/01/2020.

2.2. Mathematical model

This section presents the constructed mathematical model to solve CPSP. We present the model corresponding to scenario 1 in Section 2.2.1. Then, we make modifications on this model to solve the problem for scenario 2 and present in Section 2.2.2. The sets and indices are shared by the two models, therefore they are presented here after.

Indices

p	the population id	$\{1, \dots, P\}$
w	the week id	$\{1, \dots, W\}$
d	the day of the week	$\{1, \dots, D\}$
$scen$	the scenario id	$\{1, 2\}$
s	the site id	$\{0, 1\}$

Sets

P	the population	$\{1, \dots, 2569\}$
W	the weeks	$\{1, \dots, 60\}$
D	the days in a week	$\{1, \dots, 7\}$
FS	(p, w) : set of feasible combinations of population p and harvest week w	

In order to simplify the model without loss of generality, we decide to determine the harvesting weeks and find the planting dates with post processing. In general, the output of the ARIMA model provides the GDU forecast for the time horizon for each site, i.e., $obtGDU_{d,w,s}$. With planting date time windows information for each population, we come up with a feasible set of combinations of population p and harvest week w , i.e., FS . Then, the harvesting date is assumed to be the middle of the week, i.e., Wednesdays, to minimize the error.

2.2.1. Scenario 1 For this scenario, both sites have pre-defined capacity values for each week.

Parameters

$plSite_p$	planting site of population p
$reqGDU_p$	required GDU units for population p
$obtGDU_{d,w,s}$	obtained GDU units on day d of week w on site s
$hq_{p,scen}$	harvesting quantity of population p in scenario $scen$
$c1_{s,w}$	harvesting capacity on site s in week w for scenario 1

Parameters hq and $c1$ are used in the mathematical model whilst the rest of the parameters are used for pre-processing and post-processing.

Decision variables

$$pl_p^w = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if population } p \text{ is harvested in week } w \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$used_w = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if week } w \text{ is used for harvesting} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$m_{s,w}^+$ = the positive deviation from the capacity of harvesting week w on site s

$m_{s,w}^-$ = the negative deviation from the capacity of harvesting week w on site s

n_{w_1,w_2}^+ = the increase in harvesting quantity from week w_1 to w_2

n_{w_1,w_2}^- = the decrease in harvesting quantity from week w_1 to w_2

Objectives

The problem definition implies a multi-objective approach which is presented below.

$$\min f_1 = \sum_{w \in W} used_w \quad (1)$$

$$\min f_2 = \sum_{s,w \in W} m_{s,w}^+ + m_{s,w}^- \quad (2)$$

$$\min f_3 = \sum_{w \in W} n_w^+ + n_w^- \quad (3)$$

Objective (1) minimizes the number of weeks used for harvesting. This objective serves the aim of shortening the time horizon to harvest all the populations. Objective (2) minimizes the total deviation from the capacity for all weeks. Both the positive and negative deviation are treated equally as suggested by the problem definition. Lastly, objective (3) minimizes the total deviation of harvest quantity among two consecutive weeks to minimize the workforce fluctuation.

Constraints

$$\sum_{\substack{w \\ (p,w) \in FS}} pl_p^w = 1 \quad \forall p \in P \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{p:s=plSite_p, \\ p:(p,w) \in FS}} hq_{p,1} \cdot pl_p^w = c1_{s,w} + m_{s,w}^+ - m_{s,w}^- \quad \forall w \in W, s \in \{0,1\} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{p,w: \\ (p,w) \in FS}} pl_p^w \leq used_w \cdot M_1 \quad \forall w \in W \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{\substack{p:s=plSite_p, \\ p:(p,w) \in FS}} hq_{p,1} \cdot pl_p^w - \sum_{\substack{p:s=plSite_p, \\ p:(p,w) \in FS}} hq_{p,1} \cdot pl_p^{w+1} = n_{w,w+1}^+ - n_{w,w+1}^- \quad \forall w \in W : w \neq |W| \quad (7)$$

$$pl_p^w \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall (p, w) \in FS \quad (8)$$

$$used_w \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall w \in W \quad (9)$$

$$m_{s,w}^+, m_{s,w}^- \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in S, w \in W \quad (10)$$

$$n_{w_1,w_2}^+, n_{w_1,w_2}^- \geq 0 \quad \forall w_1 \in W, w_2 \in W \quad (11)$$

The constraint set (4) ensures that each population should be planted. Constraints (5) determine the weekly deviation from the harvesting capacity whilst constraints (6) determine which weeks are used for harvesting. Here, M_1 is a big-M value that is at most $\sum_{\substack{p,w: \\ (p,w) \in FS}} pl_p^w$. Finally, the constraint set (7) determines the difference between two consecutive days.

The rest of the constraints, i.e., (8)-(11), are domain constraints. The variables pl and $used$ are defined as binary variables whilst the deviation variables, i.e., m and n , are non-negative variables.

2.2.2. Scenario 2 For this scenario, a pre-defined capacity does not exist. Therefore, the capacity parameter in scenario 1, i.e., $c1_{s,w}$, becomes a decision variable, i.e., $c2_{s,w}$. Additional to the three objectives, we also minimize the maximum value of this variable, i.e., C_s , to determine the capacity value for scenario 2. The rest of the model remains the same. It is important to note that the modified model remains linear.

Additional decision variables

$c2_{s,w}$ harvesting capacity on site s in week w for scenario 2

C_s minimum possible capacity for site s

Additional objective

$$\min f_4 = C_s \quad (12)$$

Objective (12) minimizes the maximum capacity level over all weeks for site s .

Additional constraints

$$c2_{s,w} \leq C_s \quad \forall w \in W, s \in \{0, 1\} \quad (13)$$

$$C_s \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in S \quad (14)$$

$$c2_{s,w} \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in S, w \in W \quad (15)$$

The constraint set (13) implies that the value of C_s is bigger than the maximum of $c2_{s,w}$ among all weeks for each site s . With the help of the additional objective function 12, C_s becomes equal to the maximum of $c2_{s,w}$ for each site s . (14) and (15) imply that both C and $c2$ are non negative, respectively.

2.3. Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search

The provided instances are too large for the presented optimization problem to be solved with an exact method. Therefore, we have developed a heuristic algorithm based on the Adaptive Large Neighborhood Search meta-heuristic (ALNS, Ropke and Pisinger (2006)). ALNS provides a general framework in which to insert problem-specific information. In particular, given an existing solution, one operator o among a set of neighborhood operators O can be used to generate a new solution. The new solution is evaluated and accepted or rejected in a simulated annealing-like manner. Specifically, in the case of a multi-objective optimization problem such as the CPSP, if the new solution is not dominated by one of the solutions previously obtained, then it is always accepted. Contrarily, if the new solution is dominated, the probability of accepting it depends on the worsening of the solution and on the temperature T , which is a function of the cooling schedule of the algorithm.

At each iteration, the probability of choosing a specific operator depends on the weights assigned to all operators, which are a function of the performance of the operator. Thanks to this technique, the algorithm is able to select the most promising operators at all phases of the meta-heuristic. The pseudocode of the ALNS is presented in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: ALNS with simulated annealing

```
1 Initialize ALNS and simulated annealing parameters
2 Initialize probabilities  $P_o^0$  for each operator  $o \in O$ 
3 Start from the initial solution  $S$ . Assign  $S_{curr} \leftarrow S$ 
4 Initialize list of non-dominated solutions  $L \leftarrow \{S\}$ 
5  $Iter \leftarrow 1$ 
6 repeat
7   Draw random number to select an operator  $o \in O$  according to probabilities  $P$ 
8   Apply operator  $o$  to obtain new solution  $S_{new}$ 
9   if  $S_{new}$  is not dominated by a solution in  $L$  then
10      $S_{curr} \leftarrow S_{new}$ 
11     Add  $S_{new}$  to list  $L$ 
12     Remove from  $L$  all solutions dominated by  $S_{new}$ 
13   else
14     Calculate  $F_{new}, F_{curr}$  weighted sum of objective function values for  $S_{new}, S_{curr}$ 
15     respectively
16     Draw random probability  $r$ 
17     if  $r < \exp \frac{F_{new} - F_{curr}}{T}$  then
18        $S_{current} \leftarrow S_{new}$ 
19    $Iter \leftarrow Iter + 1$ 
20   Update probabilities  $P$  based on performance of operator  $o$ 
21   Update temperature  $T$ 
22 until  $Iter > MaxIter$ 
```

We have identified eight problem-specific operators which tackle the different objectives (1), (2), (3) and (12) of the optimization problem presented in Section 2.2. These operators combine intensification strategies that aim at making incremental improvements to the solution and diversification strategies that prevent the algorithm to be stuck in local optima, thus allowing for an exploration of the entire solution space. The operators can be categorized in five different groups. Operators 1, 2 and 3 are *rebalancing* operators which change the harvest week of some populations from high-quantity harvest weeks to low-quantity harvest weeks. Operator 4 is a *stability* operator which aims at equalizing the amount of harvest collected in consecutive weeks. Operators 5 and 6 are *emptying* operators which aim at removing all populations from a given week in order to avoid harvesting at all in that week. Operator 7 is a *capacity* operator which aims at setting the harvest quantity of a given week as close as possible to capacity. Operator 8, which is only applied in scenario 2, updates the recommended lowest location capacity.

Next, we present the pseudocodes of the eight neighborhood operators.

Algorithm 2: Operator 1

- 1 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 2 Find $w' \in W$ such that $w' = \operatorname{argmax}_{w \in W} h_w$
 - 3 Select a population $p \in P$ such that $pl_p^{w'} = 1$
 - 4 Find week w'' in the set W_p of feasible harvest weeks of p such that

$$w'' = \operatorname{argmin}_{w \in W_p} h_w \wedge h_w > 0$$
 - 5 Generate new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w'} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w''} = 1$
-

Algorithm 3: Operator 2

- 1 Draw integer r from set $\{1, \dots, 10\}$. Define set $R = \{1, \dots, r\}$
 - 2 **for** $n \in R$ **do**
 - 3 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 4 Find $w' \in W$ such that $w' = \operatorname{argmax}_{w \in W} h_w$
 - 5 Select a population $p \in P$ such that $pl_p^{w'} = 1$
 - 6 Find week w'' in the set W_p of feasible harvest weeks of p such that
 $w'' = \operatorname{argmin}_{w \in W_p} h_w \wedge h_w > 0$
 - 7 Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w'} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w''} = 1$
-

Algorithm 4: Operator 3

- 1 Draw maximum number of iteration $maxIter$ from set $\{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$
 - 2 Define a value $Q > capacity$ for the maximum desirable harvest
 - 3 $i \leftarrow 1$ **while** $\max_{w \in W} \sum_{p \in P} hq_p pl_p^w > Q \wedge i \leq maxIter$ **do**
 - 4 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 5 Find $w' \in W$ such that $w' = \operatorname{argmax}_{w \in W} h_w$
 - 6 Select a population $p \in P$ such that $pl_p^{w'} = 1$
 - 7 Find week w in the set W_p of feasible harvest weeks of p such that
 $w'' = \operatorname{argmin}_{w \in W_p} h_w \wedge h_w > 0$
 - 8 Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w'} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w''} = 1$
 - 9 $i \leftarrow i + 1$
-

Algorithm 5: Operator 4

- 1 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 2 Find $(w, w + 1) \in W$ such that $h_w > 0$, $h_{w+1} > 0$ and $|h_{w+1} - h_w|$ is maximized
 - 3 Define $w_- = \operatorname{argmin}(h_w, h_{w+1})$, $w_+ = \operatorname{argmax}(h_w, h_{w+1})$
 - 4 Select a population $p \in P$ such that $pl_p^{w_+} = 1$
 - 5 Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w_+} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w_-} = 1$
-

Algorithm 6: Operator 5

- 1 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 2 Find $(w, w + 1) \in W$ such that $h_w > 0$, $h_{w+1} > 0$ and $h_w + h_{w+1}$ is minimized
 - 3 Define $w_- = \operatorname{argmin}(h_w, h_{w+1})$, $w_+ = \operatorname{argmax}(h_w, h_{w+1})$
 - 4 **for** $p \in P : pl_p^{w_-} = 1$ **do**
 - 5 **if** w_+ is a feasible harvest week for p **then**
 - 6 \quad Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w_-} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w_+} = 1$
 - 7 **else**
 - 8 \quad Find other feasible harvest week w_{new} for p such that $h_{w_{new}} > 0$
 - 9 \quad Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w_-} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w_{new}} = 1$
-

Algorithm 7: Operator 6

- 1 Given solution S , define the vector h of the harvest quantities h_w for each week $w \in W$
 - 2 **if** $\exists w \in W : h_w = 0 \wedge h_{w+1} > 0$ **then**
 - 3 **for** $p \in P : pl_p^{w+1} = 1$ **do**
 - 4 **if** $\exists w_{new} \in W \notin w, w + 1 : w_{new}$ is a feasible harvest week for p **then**
 - 5 \quad Update new solution S^* by assigning $pl_p^{w+1} = 0$ and $pl_p^{w_{new}} = 1$
-

Algorithm 8: Operator 7

```
1 Draw integer  $r$  from set  $\{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$ . Define set  $R = \{1, \dots, r\}$ 
2 for  $n \in R$  do
3   Given solution  $S$ , define the vector  $h$  of the harvest quantities  $h_w$  for each week  $w \in W$ 
4   Select random week  $w'$  such that  $h_{w'} > 0$ 
5   while  $h_{w'} > Capacity$  do
6     Select a population  $p \in P$  such that  $pl_p^{w'} = 1$ 
7     Find week  $w_{new}$  in the set  $W_p$  of feasible harvest weeks of  $p$  such that
            $w_{new} = \operatorname{argmin}_{w \in W_p} |Capacity - (h_w + h_{q_p})|$ 
8     Update new solution  $S^*$  by assigning  $pl_p^{w'} = 0$  and  $pl_p^{w_{new}} = 1$ 
```

Algorithm 9: Operator 8 (scenario 2 only)

```
1 Calculate  $M^+ = \sum_{w \in W} m_w^+$  and  $M^- = \sum_{w \in W} m_w^-$ 
2 if  $M^+ > M^-$  then
3    $Capacity \leftarrow Capacity + 100$ 
4 else
5    $Capacity \leftarrow Capacity - 100$ 
```

3. Quantitative Results

Since we have defined a multi-objective optimization problem, the result of our algorithm is a set of non-dominated solutions, in the sense of Pareto dominance. Given the main challenge question, we have opted to favor objective (2), which minimizes the sum of the deviations between the weekly harvest and the storage capacity. Therefore, in this section, we present a solution with lowest deviation from the storage capacity, for each planting site and each scenario.

Also, for each selected solution, we have performed the Pareto analysis of the solutions obtained in the corresponding algorithm run. The analysis is done between the first objective, i.e. the number of harvest weeks, and a linear combination of the second and third objective, i.e. the deviation from the storage capacity and deviation between consecutive weeks, respectively. The second (2) and third (3) objectives are combined through the following weighted sum:

$$f^* = 0.8f_2 + 0.2f_3, \quad (16)$$

which favored again the second objective. This combination is acceptable since both objectives are expressed in the same units. The Pareto analysis of all obtained solutions, across all algorithm executions, remains part of the future work.

It should be emphasized that the algorithm successfully reduced the required number of harvest weeks along with the deviation from the available capacity, in each scenario and site. We also observed a substantial improvement of the third objective, i.e. minimization of the total deviation of harvest quantity between two consecutive weeks, for all sites and scenarios.

3.1. Scenario 1, Site 0

In Figure 6, we present the initial and final harvest quantities distributions for Scenario 1 and Site 0, in yellow and green colors, respectively. The initial harvest quantities correspond to the initial solution, while the final quantities correspond to the selected solution. Table 1 denotes objective function values for the initial and final solutions.

Figure 6 Harvest quantity results for Scenario 1 and Site 0

Table 1: Objective function values for the initial and final solutions

Objective function	Initial solution value	Final solution value
Number of harvest weeks	51	46
Deviation from the capacity	9,516,785	9,355,171
Deviation between consecutive weeks	225,228	34,738

From the final solution, we can see that the algorithm has succeeded to create three periods with fairly constant weekly harvest quantities: 1) from week 19 to week 38, 2) from week 39 to week 45, and 3) from week 56 to week 69. The latter two periods have weekly harvest quantities very close to the capacity of 7000. The presented result indicates the correctness of the logic of developed algorithm operators.

Figure 7 Pareto diagram of results for Scenario 1 and Site 0

The Pareto diagram of the solutions obtained in the same algorithm execution as the selected solution is presented in Fig. 7. Here, the selected solution is denoted with a green rectangle, while the initial solution is denoted with a red one. From the diagram, we can observe that there is no favorable trade-off between the two solutions, since by favoring the derived objective f^* , we have a clear worsening of the objective (1).

3.2. Scenario 1, Site 1

In Figure 8, we present the initial (represented by the yellow bars) and final (green bars) harvest quantities distributions, corresponding to the initial and selected solutions, respectively, for Scenario 1 and Site 1.

Table 2 denotes objective function values for the initial and final solutions.

For this site, the algorithm was not as successful as for Site 0. Nevertheless, the results demonstrated the algorithm tendency towards equalizing the weekly harvest amounts.

Figure 8 Harvest quantity results for Scenario 1 and Site 1

Table 2: Objective function values for the initial and final solutions

Objective function	Initial solution value	Final solution value
Number of harvest weeks	38	34
Deviation from the capacity	7,120,205	7,090,845
Deviation between consecutive weeks	242,630	135,486

Fig. 9 presents the solutions obtained in the same algorithm execution as the selected solution for Scenario 1 and Site 1, in the form of Pareto diagram. Here, the selected solution is denoted with a green rectangle, while the initial solution is denoted with a red one. In the diagram, we can see that there are pairs of solutions which offer even better improvement of the objective f^* with a smaller increase in the harvest weeks number, such as between the solutions with 28 and 29 harvest weeks,

Figure 9 Pareto diagram of results for Scenario 1 and Site 1

or solutions with 30 and 31 harvest weeks. These solutions should also be taken in to account if the objective (2) were not considered as the most important.

3.3. Scenario 2, Site 0

In Figure 10, we present the initial and final harvest quantities distributions for Scenario 2 and Site 0, in yellow and green colors, respectively. Table 3 denotes objective function values for the initial and final solutions.

Again, for Site 0, the algorithm has managed to equalize the weekly harvest to a great extent, especially between 20th and 37th harvest week.

Regarding the additional objective from Scenario 2, i.e. finding the minimal storage capacity, the result showed that the current capacity performs best. In fact, the found solutions with increased capacity only increased the harvest amount deviation from the capacity. We believe that the reason for this is the setting of the task, i.e. the given earliest and latest planting dates for the populations. However, this remains an assumption which we need yet to check.

Figure 10 Harvest quantity results for Scenario 2 and Site 0

The Pareto diagram of the solutions obtained in the same algorithm execution as the selected solution for Scenario 2 and Site 0 is presented in Fig. 11. Here, the selected and initial solutions are marked with a green and red rectangles, respectively. Again, we cannot observe a clearly favorable trade-off between the two obtained solutions, which makes both solutions potentially useful.

Table 3: Objective function values for the initial and final solutions

Objective function	Initial solution value	Final solution value
Number of harvest weeks	51	48
Deviation from the capacity	9,582,540	9,457,250
Deviation between consecutive weeks	321,472	56,136
Minimum storage capacity	7000	7000

Figure 11 Pareto diagram of results for Scenario 2 and Site 0

3.4. Scenario 2, Site 1

In Figure 12, we present the initial and final harvest quantities distributions for Scenario 2 and Site 1, in yellow and green colors, respectively. Table 4 denotes objective function values for the initial and final solutions.

Table 4: Objective function values for the initial and final solutions

Objective function	Initial solution value	Final solution value
Number of harvest weeks	38	35
Deviation from the capacity	7,209,088	7,177,366
Deviation between consecutive weeks	345,422	165,344
Minimum storage capacity	6000	6000

Similar to the results for Site 1 in Scenario 1, the algorithm have reduced the oscillations in the weekly harvest amounts compared to the initial planting schedule. Additionally, the algorithm was

Figure 12 Harvest quantity results for Scenario 2 and Site 1

able to reduce the number of isolated harvest weeks, which are those weeks that are preceded and succeeded by weeks with no harvest, such as weeks 21 and 24 in the original solution.

In Figure 13, we show the Pareto diagram of the solutions obtained in the same algorithm execution as the selected solution for Scenario 2 and Site 1. Here, the selected and initial solutions are marked with a green and red rectangles, respectively. As in the previous case, a most favorable trade-off between the obtained solutions cannot be determined clearly. Therefore, all three found solutions could be taken into account under different optimization goals.

3.5. Algorithm performance

The algorithm has been developed in python programming language. The algorithm was tested on Intel Core i5 CPU at 1.8 GHz, using 8 GB of RAM. The execution time for one scenario and one site is between 30 and 40 minutes with 30 temperature drops for simulated annealing and 1000 iterations at each temperature.

Figure 13 Pareto diagram of results for Scenario 2 and Site 1

4. Conclusion

In this report, we have presented a heuristic algorithm to solve the Crop Planting Schedule Problem. The algorithm is based on the ALNS metaheuristic. This choice has been based on our previous research experiences where ALNS proved to be a very powerful tool for solving large combinatorial optimization problems, similar to CPSP. The algorithm succeeds at finding solutions that considerably improve the initial planting schedule. Due to the complexity of the problem, we believe that an exact method cannot to be used to solve the given data instance.

Establishing a precise relation between planting and harvest dates for each population is fundamental to obtain valuable results from the ALNS-based heuristic. For this purpose, we devoted a substantial effort to create a precise GDU forecasting model, which we based on ARIMA models.

Although the found solutions improve the planting schedule to a notable extent, we have identified several possibilities for further development of our algorithm. Firstly, the current operators tend occasionally to concentrate solutions around local minima. Hence, we need to increase the

diversification of the operators used for exploring the search space, especially the ones exploring minimal storage capacities, used in Scenario 2. Secondly, the other metaheuristics and search space strategies, e.g. Variable Neighborhood Search, should be tested and their results compared with the ones obtained by the current approach. Thirdly, other approaches for GDU forecasting, e.g. Winter-Holt method or neural networks, should be investigated. Finally, we are aware that our optimization algorithm is currently sensitive to the GDUs forecast. To overcome this, we intend to direct our future research in the direction of robust optimization and its solution methods.

5. Team Members

The team is composed of the following researchers:

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NB: All team members contributed equally to the presented research work and results.

6. Supplementary Materials

Together with this report, we submit the selected solutions in the requested CSV format. The following Table 5 lists the files with the solution for each scenario and site.

Table 5: Summary of the submitted solution files.

Scenario	Site	Harvest amount file	Planting dates file
1	0	HarvestQuantity_sce_1_site_0.csv	PlantingDates_sce_1_site_0.csv
1	1	HarvestQuantity_sce_1_site_1.csv	PlantingDates_sce_1_site_1.csv
2	0	HarvestQuantity_sce_2_site_0.csv	PlantingDates_sce_2_site_0.csv
2	1	HarvestQuantity_sce_2_site_1.csv	PlantingDates_sce_2_site_1.csv

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